

Deliverable 6.1

Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Activities

Version 1.0

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ERINN Innovation Ltd.

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UK Research
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Executive Summary

The EmpowerUs Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Activities (PDEC) outlines the EC rights and obligations of the consortium to exploitation, dissemination and communication of project results. It adopts EC best practice guidelines and defines the objectives of EmpowerUs' communication, dissemination and exploitation. It also identifies target stakeholders, proposes communication tools and channels, and outlines responsibilities and resources to carry out effective knowledge management and to measure impact.

All project partners have an obligation to participate in the dissemination, communication and exploitation of EmpowerUs results and outputs to create impact, especially in their own countries and in their own communities. Within the PDEC, the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities to be performed are described, along with protocols and processes to be followed.

EmpowerUs has a work package dedicated to these activities (WP6, led by ERINN Innovation), specifically designed to support project communication activities to a wide audience and targeted dissemination and exploitation of results to specific stakeholders. To support partners in the communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, a portfolio of resources has been developed under WP6. This portfolio will be updated regularly and additional resources made available as required. EmpowerUs will make use of the latest tools and communication channels to ensure cost effectiveness and maximum impact.

The PDEC has been developed by ERINN Innovation, who will also oversee its continuous implementation. This is the first version of the PDEC and as it is a dynamic document, it will be evaluated throughout the project and updated at EC reporting stages.

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1. Introduction

EmpowerUs aims to empower coastal communities as users of the sea to act for change to ensure sustainable coastal development. Coastal communities face many challenges including extreme weather associated with climate change, increased pressures from urban development and tourism, as well as changes in traditional and cultural practices. When faced with such a myriad of ever-changing challenges, it can be difficult to adapt. Recognising that these complex challenges require multiple, integrated solutions, EmpowerUs will support coastal communities to create multiple, integrated and flexible solutions to support their transition towards more sustainable, inclusive and resilient coastal development.

To guarantee the adoption of EmpowerUs solutions, support the uptake and to maximise the impact and legacy of EmpowerUs, the project has put in place effective communication, dissemination, engagement and knowledge transfer strategies in a standalone work package (WP6: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Ocean Literacy) in which all partners participate.

1.1 Rationale

The EmpowerUs PDEC outlines the exploitation, dissemination and communication strategies to be implemented by the consortium throughout the project lifetime and beyond.

Adopting the EC's best practice guidelines and aligning with rights and obligations outlined in the EmpowerUs Grant Agreement related to dissemination and exploitation, the PDEC describes internal processes and protocols set up to support communication, manage generated knowledge and to ensure the exploitation of EmpowerUs results. It identifies key project stakeholders, communication tools and channels and describes the means (tools, messages) of dissemination and measures to support exploitation.

1.2 Objectives

The PDEC aims to:

- Provide a useful guide to all members of the EmpowerUs consortium about rules and responsibilities surrounding communication, dissemination, and exploitation.
- Promote the project activities and results beyond the consortium by employing a range of communication and dissemination tools.
- Identify and profile the target stakeholders for the different project results.
- Define the most effective dissemination and exploitation channels, tools, and means, tailored to the relevant stakeholders.
- Outline the knowledge management and transfer principles and protocols to ensure effective transfer of Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- Ensure timely and efficient knowledge management and transfer while safeguarding intellectual property (IP).
- Maximise post-project uptake by developing thorough and forward-thinking plans that clearly outline the potential users and applications of the project's KERs and Knowledge Transfer (KT) activities required to ensure objective and measurable short and long-term project impacts.

The EmpowerUs Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Activities (PDEC) describes the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities to be performed to ensure the

exploitation of the project's outputs, its maximum impact, and the availability of the gained knowledge for all interested organisations. It is a dynamic document and will be evaluated and updated at M18 (March 2024) and M36 (September 2025) of the project, allowing for adjustments as needed.

2. Key Principles Guiding the PDEC

2.1 Definitions and Terminology

The foundation of the EmpowerUs PDEC is the knowledge management process which has been implemented from the start of the project and which informs communication, dissemination, and exploitation. EmpowerUs distinguishes between communication, dissemination, and exploitation (knowledge transfer), in line with the European Commission (EC) definitions¹ as follows:

- **Communication** is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime. It is aimed at promoting EmpowerUs and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about EmpowerUs and the project's results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Activities used for communication purposes are, for example, a public website, social media, or a newsletter.
- **Dissemination** is the public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protection or exploiting the results), including scientific publication in any medium. Activities used for dissemination purposes are, for example, conferences, education and training events, clustering activities, and collaboration with EU-funded projects.
- **Knowledge transfer and exploitation of results** is more advanced than communication and dissemination and involves the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities, or feeding back into policy-making activities.

2.2 Rights, Rules and Obligations related to Results

This section outlines a summary of some key aspects of the rights and obligations relating to the protection of these results; however it is not an exhaustive summary. For further details on the project and Horizon Europe rules surrounding ownership and protection of results please refer to the Grant Agreement (GA), Consortium Agreement (CA), and for specific rules on data outputs, please see D6.2 Data Management Plan (DMP; due in M6).

2.2.1 Ownership of Results

Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them. Two or more beneficiaries' own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or separate them, for the purpose of applying for, obtaining, or maintaining their protection (GA Article 16 – Annex 5). The joint owners must agree (in writing) on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership (joint ownership agreement), to ensure compliance with

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/temp-form/report/periodic-report_horizon- Euratom_en.pdf

their obligations under the GA. If valuable results are not protected, the Commission may under certain circumstances assume ownership of the results (see GA Article 16 – Annex 5 for further details).

2.2.2 Protection of Results

Each beneficiary has an obligation to protect its results. Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must adequately protect their results — for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage — if protection is possible and justified, taking into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, the legitimate interests of the other beneficiaries and any other legitimate interests.

2.2.3 Exploitation of Results

Each beneficiary has an obligation to exploit its results. Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must — up to four years after the end of the action - use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.

If, despite a beneficiary's best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results (see GA Article 16 – Annex 5 for further details). Beneficiaries must also continue to use their best efforts to exploit their results themselves throughout the subsequent three years.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) & Management

EmpowerUs will follow the rules for IP set out by the EC, as regulated. More information can be found in GA Article 16 – Annex 5: "Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) — Background and Results — Access Rights and Rights of Use".

The partners will ensure that adequate steps towards protection are taken prior to exploitation, dissemination, and communication, preventing unapproved public disclosure of results, tools, products and services. An IP assessment form for screening dissemination, exploitation and communication activities will be created and shared on SharePoint for partners to fill out to ensure protection of results.

2.2.4 Communication and Dissemination of Results

Each beneficiary must disseminate their results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public. However, no dissemination may take place before a decision is made regarding possible protection (section 2.2.4). Other participants may object if their legitimate interests in relation to their foreground or background could potentially suffer harm.

Beneficiaries that intend to disseminate their results must give at least 15 calendar days advance notice (**Prior Notice**) to the other beneficiaries, unless agreed otherwise, together with sufficient information on the results they will disseminate (GA Article 17 – Annex 5).

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Notwithstanding the above, certain dissemination activities which, by their nature, must be carried out in a timely manner (e.g. social media posts, promotional articles and reports) will be exempt from the obligation to give prior notice to all partners so as not to impede the project's dissemination strategy, provided that all EmpowerUs beneficiaries engaged in such dissemination are in agreement prior to such dissemination and provided that the duty of confidentiality is respected (GA Article 13).

For all types of Publications, Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities (including scientific publications, oral and poster presentations, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications, etc.) where EmpowerUs results or outputs are presented, the Prior Notice Procedure (protocol below) must be applied.

PROTOCOL – Prior Notice Procedure

Upload the planned publication (full draft, if possible, but at a minimum this must include an abstract and details on where it will be published or presented) and/or presentation to the project [SharePoint Prior Notice folder](#) and inform the partnership of their intent via email at least 15 calendar days before publishing (see above). Partners should use the Prior Notice email template, available in the Prior Notice folder.

Partners have 15 days to object in writing to the author.

Any objection needs to be justified and precise suggested modifications given. An objection is justified if:

- It adversely affects protection of results/background of the objecting party.
- Legitimate interests of the objecting party would be significantly harmed.

Please send the objection to the author, and cc the following people:

ERINN: donnchadh@erinn.eu, annette@erinn.eu

NRI: mbj@nforsk.no, cbr@nforsk.no

If no objection is raised within this time, or if objections are addressed and accepted by the objecting partner, the publication may then be submitted.

Open Science and Open Access to Scientific Publications

Open Science (or Open Research) is a broad term describing the transparent and collaborative approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusion of knowledge. Open Access (OA) is specifically applied to research outputs (publications, articles, data, books etc). This section outlines OA requirements for publications. For more information on open science in relation to research data and FAIR principles, please see the EmpowerUs Data Management Plan (D6.2 – DMP).

Providing open access to publications in Horizon Europe funded projects is an obligation for all grants. All beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results (GA Article 17 – Annex 5), and must:

- As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- And, at the same time, provide information (about the research output, tools or instruments) needed to validate the conclusion of the scientific publication via the repository. Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- Ensure open access, via the repository, to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication, including at least the following: publication (author(s), identifying those involved in the action, title, date of publication, publication venue); the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”; the name of the project (“Socio-economic Empowerment of coastal communities as users of the sea to ensure sustainable coastal development”), acronym (“EmpowerUs”) and grant number (“101059957”); licensing terms; persistent identifiers. Metadata of deposited publications must be open (CC0 “No Rights Reserved” or equivalent) and in line with the FAIR principles (see D6.2 – Data Management Plan).

There are three **Open Access Categories**²:

- **‘Publisher Open’** often referred to as ‘gold’, ‘hybrid’ or bronze’ open access where an article is published in an open access journal or is accessible in a subscription journal. The final edited version of the publication can be read directly from the publisher’s website, usually immediately on publication.
- **‘Other Platform Open’** referred to as ‘green’ or ‘grey’ open access where the publication is shared online via a repository or website. A pre-print version of already existing or new articles can be uploaded to a domain specific, institutional other repository, generally without any extra cost.
- **‘Closed’** where the publication is not open and is closed to access.

Within the **Publisher Open** category, and as part of the EC’s continuous reporting requirements of publications (see Section 3.2), beneficiaries must indicate whether the publishing venue is ‘hybrid’, ‘full open access’ or ‘full subscription’.

a) **Hybrid** means that the published article or final peer-reviewed manuscript is made accessible in a subscription journal with an open license. This involves making articles available in older journals that were historically subscription-based and have not transitioned to fully open access. This route almost always involves payment of an APC or some form of institutional payment through a “read and publish” agreement.

b) **Full Open Access** means that the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is published in an Open Access (OA) journal. To qualify as an OA journal there must be clear re-use rights and certain quality measures need to be validated by the Directory of Open Access Journals.

c) **Full Subscription** means that the published article or final peer-reviewed manuscript is made accessible in a Subscription Publisher with no reuse rights. Publishers sometimes make articles

² <https://open.coki.ac/open/>

available for limited periods or without guarantees. This makes more articles readable but doesn't ensure long term accessibility.

Under the Horizon Europe programme, 'Publisher Open' and 'Other Platform Open' are permitted (see above), however only publication fees in 'full open access' or 'full subscription' venues are eligible for reimbursement (Article 17 – Annex 5).

For more information on open access, please consult GA Article 17 – Annex 5 (Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility).

Visibility of funding

Partners are obligated to use the EU emblem when publishing and/or presenting work carried out under the EmpowerUs project (GA Article 17.2). Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must display the EU emblem. This includes conferences, seminars, in information material (such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc.), including electronic form via social media, etc. and any infrastructure, equipment or major result funded by the grant. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the partners may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Partners are obligated to use the UKRI logo when publishing and/or presenting work carried out under the EmpowerUs project in which UK partners (QUB) are involved. When displayed in association with the UKRI logo or any other logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the project must include the following acknowledgement and emblem:

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101059957 (EmpowerUs). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the project in which UK partners (QUB) are involved must include the acknowledgement and emblem above, as well as the following UKRI funding acknowledgement and logo:

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101059957 (EmpowerUs). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK participants in EmpowerUs are supported by UKRI Grant No. 10040189 (QUB).

The EU emblem, UKRI logo and disclaimer graphics are available on the project SharePoint. If you have any queries about the use of this disclaimer, please contact ERINN Innovation (donnchadh@erinn.eu).

2.3 General Data Protection Regulation Implications

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679) provides enhanced protection to individuals' data privacy rights. Organisations storing or using personal data (anything that allows identification of an individual) must clearly disclose what data is being collected and how, why it is being processed/used, how long it is being retained, and if it is being shared with any third parties. Personal data can be names, email addresses, job titles, phone numbers, and anything that allows identification of an individual.

2.3.1 GDPR compliance (website, mailing list and events)

The EmpowerUs project website (www.empowerus-project.eu) managed by ERINN Innovation, is fully compliant with GDPR by incorporating a Privacy Statement and Cookie Bar informing website visitors about what EmpowerUs does with any personal data gathered. A 'Subscribe to News' button is clearly visible on the Home Page, allowing people to voluntarily sign up to the EmpowerUs mailing list. The sign-up page contains a link to the Privacy Statement, and subscription is on a double opt-in basis, whereby people who sign up need to confirm their email address to complete the subscription process. This ensures compliance regarding consent under GDPR. The subscription system sends an automatic EmpowerUs email to the subscriber who then needs to click on the link in the email sent to them. The mailing list will only be used to share EmpowerUs-related information and news. Photographs and videos taken at EmpowerUs project events, workshops, meetings and promotional activities will comply with the GDPR through the use of consent forms to be signed by all persons involved. Personal data collected at events will be stored on secure databases and will not be used /shared for any other purpose. For more information on the use of Personal Data and associated ethics, please see D7.1 – OEI Requirement No 1.

3. Post-Dissemination Requirements – Continuous Reporting

3.1 Continuous Reporting of Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities

As part of the EU contractual requirements, all scientific publications, dissemination activities and communication activities are reported as part of the continuous reporting of the project in the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal.

NOTE: Data on all dissemination activities and communication activities will be collated and uploaded to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal by ERINN. Beneficiaries do NOT need to upload this information to the portal. To successfully manage the dissemination activities and communication activities, we require all partners to routinely update the "EmpowerUs Continuous Reporting Log" which will be shared with all partners and located in the SharePoint folder.

3.2 Continuous Reporting of Scientific Publications

Scientific publications must be uploaded to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal once they have been accepted for publication. This includes articles in journals, publications in conference proceedings/workshops, books/monographs, chapters in a book, thesis/dissertation, etc.

NOTE: Publications will be collated and uploaded to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal by ERINN. Beneficiaries do NOT need to upload this information to the portal. Partners are encouraged to send their publications to ERINN (donnchadh@erinn.eu) and NRI (mbj@nforsk.no, cbr@nforsk.no) as soon as available and no later than three months after the official publication date, see detailed instructions below.

PROTOCOL – EC Reporting on Publications, Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities

- All partners will be required to keep track of all their scientific publications, dissemination activities and communication activities during project implementation.
- The “EmpowerUs Continuous Reporting Log” has been developed by ERINN to support the reporting of these activities. The Continuous Reporting Log has been shared with all partners on SharePoint.
- Partners should regularly contribute information to update the log, this contains separate worksheets to report on 1) Publications and 2) Dissemination Activities and 3) Communication Activities.
- The log will be reviewed by ERINN for completeness and correctness at EC reporting periods.

***Note: Please do not change anything directly on the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal yourself in relation to dissemination or publication activities. ERINN will upload the communication activities, dissemination activities and publications to the portal.**

3.3 Patents (IPR) Reporting

EmpowerUs partners are responsible for tracking their Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and innovation activities resulting from the project. Whenever new IPR has been filed (the EC recommends filing with the European Patent Office), partners are required to email the relevant information to the Innovation Board Chair (ERINN: annette@erinn.eu, donnchadh@erinn.eu). ERINN will then be responsible for uploading the required information to the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal.

The partners are required to provide ERINN with the following:

- Identification of IPR type and Confidentiality
- Type of IPR (Patent/Trademark/Registered Design/Utility Model/Other)
- Confidentiality (Yes/No)
- Application Title
- Embargo end date

3.4 Datasets

EmpowerUs partners are responsible for recording all datasets resulting from the project. For more information on datasets, please refer to the Data Management Plan (D6.2).

3.5 Overview of Continuous Reporting Procedures

Item	Action needed by acting partner	Partner Uploading to EC Portal
Scientific Publications	Log Publication in the ‘EmpowerUs Continuous Reporting Log’.	ERINN

Communication Activities	Regularly log all communication activities in the 'EmpowerUs Continuous Reporting Log'.	ERINN
Dissemination Activities	Regularly log all dissemination activities in the 'EmpowerUs Continuous Reporting Log'.	ERINN
Patents/IPR	Email ERINN the required information	ERINN
Datasets	Log all datasets in the 'EmpowerUs Continuous Reporting Log'.	ATU

4. Stakeholder Engagement

The purpose of the engagement activities described in the EmpowerUs PDEC is to facilitate dialogue, build relationships and generate exchanges between EmpowerUs and relevant stakeholders as described below.

4.1 Internal Stakeholders - Project Bodies

Innovation Board

The Innovation Board is chaired by ERINN and consists of five other members of the consortium (see Table 1). The Innovation Board will work closely with the coordinator and other management and advisory boards and will be responsible for coordinating the analysis of project results. The Innovation Board will implement knowledge management methodologies and deliver Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) for the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

Table 1. Innovation Board Members

Name	Organisation	Email
Annette Wilson (Chair)	ERINN	annette@erinn.eu
Salem Gharbia	ITS	salem.gharbia@atu.ie
Ida G. Jørgensen	KPH	igi@kph.no
Christian B. Ekeland	NRI	Cbe@nforsk.no
Brendan Murtagh	QUB	b.murtagh@qub.ac.uk
Marie Vandewalle	UFZ	marie.vandewalle@ufz.de

International Advisory Board

The International Advisory Board consists of five leading global transdisciplinary experts (see Table 2), including the EmpowerUs project coordinator, whose involvement will add value to the overall project development, knowledge and innovation creation of the project. The International Advisory Board does not have decision authority in the project but will provide inputs and feedback on the progress and results of the project, advise on links with relevant interest groups outside EmpowerUs, propose and encourage the potential interactions of the project with other projects, initiatives and activities. It will also advise on the selection and transfer of the project's KERs.

Table 2. International Advisory Board Members

Name	Organisation	Expertise	Email
Maiken Bjørkan (Chair)	NRI	EmpowerUs Project Coordinator	mbj@nforsk.no
Josef Settele	UFZ	IPBES secretariat, and expert in ecology, climate change and interdisciplinary studies	josef.settele@ufz.de
Juliette Young	INRA	IPBES expert in Policy support tools and Transformative change assessment	juliette.young@inrae.fr
Emma Bello Gomez	EuroMarine	Project manager, Prep4Blue and leader of the EuroMarine Network	director@euromarinetwork.eu
Froukje Platjouw	NIVA	Expert in the field of EU and international environmental law.	Froukje.Platjouw@niva.no

Steering Committee

The Steering Committee consists of the coordinator and representatives of the consortium appointed to it by the General Assembly. In addition to the WP leads, the Steering Committee also consists of the Data Management Plan lead and the Gender, Diversity and Equality lead. The Steering Committee shall monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the project, including giving advice on the selection and transfer of the project's KERs.

4.2 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

To engage with its stakeholders, EmpowerUs will implement a structured knowledge management and transfer methodology (Section 5). By focusing on Individual Outputs and associated Impact Plans, appropriate targets and end users will be identified, along with potential application and exploitation routes. Based on the concept of "co-creation", Stakeholder engagement takes many shapes within the planned activities of the project's work packages (Table 3).

Table 3. Types of stakeholder engagement and examples in the project

Type of Stakeholder Engagement	Examples of Stakeholder Engagement within EmpowerUs		
Informative Engagement (diffusion)	WP1: Ensure effective communications between the project consortium and the European Commission	WP5: Roadmap, Handbook and Policy Briefs to inform stakeholders (scientists, policymakers, citizens and society) about project methodologies and results	WP6: Communication and awareness raising about the project and dissemination of results via visual assets (factsheet, poster, banner, graphics, video)
Consultative Engagement (utilisation)	WP2: Community governance audit – interviews with local stakeholders to assess	WP3: Q-method surveys with local stakeholders in the TCLs to measure project impact	WP6: Collection of Blue Justice Stories through interviews with local stakeholders in the TCLs

	local community governance arrangements in TCLs		
Collaborative Engagement (learning and co-creation)	WP2: Real-life testing of Tailored Empowerment Programmes in TCLs; Implementation, testing and assessment of pilot interventions in TCLs	WP3: Design, development and implementation of Workshop 1 (Participatory Future Scenarios) in TCLs	WP4: Design, development and implementation of Workshop 2 (Co-development of TEPs) in TCLs

The consortium has extensive experience in multinational, multi-lingual, multi-disciplinary and multi-partner collaborative research and innovation activities, and in effective communication of progress and results. By applying the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, we have identified these various groups in society to have a vested interest in the EmpowerUs results (Table 4).

Table 4. Likely end-users of EmpowerUs KERs

Stakeholder group	Specific Stakeholders
Academics and Scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social and political scientists (in socioeconomics, outreach/citizen science, gender, equality, social transition) • Marine, environmental and climate scientists • Researchers in Marine Spatial Planning and Integrated Coastal Zone Management • Researchers in Engineering • Researchers in Nature-based Solutions
Policy and Decision Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission • European Parliament • National, regional, local authorities • Public bodies • Municipal departments • Coastal managers, planners, licensing authorities
Business/Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fisheries, aquaculture, farmers, small/large scale producers • Tourism and related businesses • Private business investors • Start-ups, incubators, (social) entrepreneurs, local business support networks
Citizens and society as a whole	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen interest groups • Community action and youth groups • Local activists • People of influence • Teachers in formal education bodies (schools) • Educators in other institutions: aquaria, museums • Local OL/Conservation groups • Potentially disempowered groups (Women, Indigenous people, Migrants, Young people) • General public (Broader society, Not-for-profit organisations, Civil society, Media)
Other EU projects and networks in similar domains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU projects: Sea Change, ResponSEABLE, Sea for Society, SCORE, PREP4BLUE, PERMAGOV, CrossGov • Ocean Literacy Networks (e.g. EU4Ocean Coalition for Ocean Literacy, Irish Ocean Literacy Network) • International Advisory Board • EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters

The EmpowerUs Stakeholder Engagement Strategy is outlined below in Table 5. It includes the objectives, activities and expected impact of engagement per main stakeholder group throughout the full project duration.

Table 5. EmpowerUs Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Target and user groups	Tools of Engagement	Expected Impact
Academics and Scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing peer-reviewed articles in OA journals, popularised field-specific magazine • Oral / Poster presentations at transdisciplinary conferences, workshops and events (see section 7) • Data published in OA repositories • Public deliverables • Participation in the Eclipse Expert Working Group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer of new knowledge • Raise awareness of the project results • Reuse of the project's scientific data • Boost the project sustainability through the development of new related research projects
Policy and Decision makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roadmap (D5.1), Handbook (D5.2), Policy briefs (D2.3, D4.3, D5.3) • Participation and presentation of the project results at events (e.g. Final event – M36) • Focus group meeting with EC Knowledge centre for Biodiversity (T4.1) • Dialogue meetings at municipal level • Presentation of the project results at high-level conferences / to advisory bodies • OL activities directed at policy and regulatory bodies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positively influence policy and support the achievement of the EU Green Deal to become net carbon-neutral by 2050 • Contribute to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the implementation of the Maritime Spatial Planning and the Integrated Maritime Policy (including the Water Framework Directive and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive), the EU Rural Vision, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the EU Adaptation Strategy
Businesses/Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website, news articles, blogs (e.g. TCL blogs) • Publications in sector specific and industry relevant magazines • Workshops, OL activities • Delivery of TEPs • Dialogue meetings at municipal level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate the business potential and opportunities for ensuring sustainable, inclusive and resilient coastal development, resulting in the creation of more sustainable coastal economies, long term benefits to businesses in the surrounding

		communities and positive environmental change
Citizens and society as a whole	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website, news articles, blogs (e.g. TCL blogs) • Project branding & promotional materials (factsheets, banners) • Media campaigns, press releases • Social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn) and campaigns • Engagement with relevant activists and influencers • Inspiring audio-visual material (video clips, vlogs, GIFs) • Infographics • EmpowerUs StoryMap (T6.4) • OL activities • Final event/exhibition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase citizens' participation in EmpowerUs-related activities • Increased awareness of the benefits of positive interactions with the coast and nature-connectedness • Raise awareness on the importance of EmpowerUs for the future, and inform about the benefits of the project towards sustainable, inclusive and resilient communities
Other EU projects and networks in similar domains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitations to EmpowerUs events • (Joint) Presentations at conferences • (Joint) Participation in workshops from other projects • Joint events with EU projects from other calls • Involvement in Advisory Board 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stronger collaborations and networks • Increased opportunities to work together, coordinated research efforts and better use of resources • Coordinated dissemination activities in order to maximise project impact, exchange on R&D results and improve robustness of project results

4.3 EmpowerUs-Specific Stakeholder Events

Workshop 1: Participatory Future Scenario Workshop

Workshop 1 on Participatory Future Scenarios will be organised in the first year of the project (T3.1) and will be carried out in each of the TCLs, making a total of 6 workshops (see Table 6). The workshops will be attended by local stakeholders from the TCLs and will explore the co-creation of desired futures for the local communities in the TCLs.

Table 6. Workshop 1 Schedule

Transition Coastal Lab	Date for Workshop 1
Norway	4 th May 2023
Cyprus	23 rd May 2023
Finland	31 st May 2023

Spain	3 rd June 2023
Bulgaria	13 th June 2023
Ireland	19 th June 2023

Workshop 2: Co-develop TEPs to be tested in pilots

Workshop 2 will focus on co-developing Tailored Empowerment Programmes with the TCLs that will be tested in the local areas. Workshop 2 will be organised in the second year of the project (T4.3) and will be carried out in each of the TCLs, making a total of 6 workshops.

Ocean Literacy Activities

Ocean Literacy activities will be organised throughout the second and third years of the project (after Workshop 2). Two Ocean Literacy activities will be hosted in each TCL, where local stakeholders will take part in the activities and use the resources. A total of 12 Ocean Literacy activities will take place.

Final Event

The final event for the project will be organised around European Maritime Day 2025 and will showcase the results of the project in open workshop-style demonstrations for all relevant stakeholders.

5. Knowledge Management, Transfer & Exploitation of Results

5.1 Knowledge Management & Transfer Overview

The European Commission has identified the importance of improving knowledge transfer between public research institutions and third parties, including industry and civil society organisations, as one of ten key areas for action³. EmpowerUs will employ a proven Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology to effectively address this key aspect of facilitating project impact.

This methodology was originally developed in the FP7 MarineTT project (GA #244164), and further developed and applied by the H2020 COLUMBUS project (GA #652690 - www.columbusproject.eu). This methodology has been applied in many FP7, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe funded projects such as AQUAEXCEL, AQUAEXCEL2020, Aqualnova, ARRAINA, COEXIST, COMMON SENSE, ECsafeSEAFOOD, MaCuMBA, MG4U, ParaFishControl, MATES, SIMBA, ERGO, REvived water, RES4BUILD, SEALIVE, BIOGEARS, SEArctularMINE, TechOceanS, WaterLANDS and PREP4BLUE.

Knowledge Management is the process of identifying, capturing, organising, analysing, and storing knowledge to ensure its availability to be transferred effectively to specific and relevant users.

Knowledge Transfer (KT) is the overall process of moving knowledge from knowledge sources to targeted potential users of the knowledge, focusing the research being conducted on the wider needs of society and industry⁴. KT consists of a range of activities that aims to capture and transmit knowledge, skills, and competence from those who generate them to those who will transform them into added value outcomes. It encompasses both commercial and non-commercial activities such as research collaborations, consultancy, licensing, spin-off creation, research mobility, and publications.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/pdf/download_en/knowledge_transfe_07.pdf

⁴ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-07-127_en.htm?locale=en

The ultimate end benefit of successful KT is the application and influence of knowledge on targeted communities with greater impact (short and long term) across academia, industry and society.

Knowledge Outputs (KOs) are described as “a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a scientific project. It is not limited to *de-novo* or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge”. Typically, such knowledge might be referenced as a small part of a published paper, potentially three to five years after the approach is pioneered in a research project.

Key Exploitable Results (KERs) within EmpowerUs are tangible or intangible outputs of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature⁵ which have been deemed to be of **high priority** for project transfer actions. The means by which KERs will be identified from KOs is described in this section, but it is important to note that EmpowerUs is not implying any sort of value judgement between KOs and KERs. Rather, the project is simply using this distinction to allow knowledge that is of the most direct impact to the project, or is most feasibly transferable by the project, to be prioritised when assigning resources for transfer. By focusing on identifying KERs and transferring them when they have been assessed as having potential application and impact, it is possible to fast track them, providing a faster impact on target- and end-users external to the project.

End User(s) are the individual(s) who are identified as being in a position where they could feasibly **apply** a given unit of Knowledge (KO/KER) and by doing so create the desired eventual impact of that knowledge. The KO/KER may need to **evolve** in order to reach the end user.

Target User is an individual(s) (organisations should be avoided where possible as specificity is crucial), whose position makes them a potential stepping-stone needed for a KO/KER to progress towards an identified end user and eventual impact. Target users are individuals with a specific mandate or responsibilities relevant to the specific KO/KER being evaluated. Target users should not merely be potential users of knowledge but should be individuals whose application of the knowledge is likely to advance it down the Pathway to Impact.

A **Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP)** is an informed stepwise plan for achieving the identified eventual impact of any piece of knowledge, regardless of whether this impact is achievable in the short, medium or long term. In EmpowerUs these will be developed for all selected KERs. The KTP identifies the end user capable of producing the desired eventual impact and outlines a specific series of transfer activities to intermediate target users.

Eventual Impact is the ultimate end benefit of the application of the knowledge (KO/KER). It is defined as an overall enhanced situation, generally for society but it can also be research or industry specific. Eventual impacts can be the adoption of new technologies, products or innovation identified and refined within the project, or a change in protocols.

The Knowledge Management and Transfer of EmpowerUs KERs is integrated into the project through WP6 and is based on regularly collecting KOs/KERs through structured templates and interviews with partners responsible for developing the results. Collected results will be assessed by the Innovation Board based on criteria related to their innovation capacity, relevance to the sector, and expected impact. Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) will be developed for individual or clusters of KERs assessed

⁵ <https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/>

as being of high potential for contributing to the project’s objectives. This customised approach will increase the likelihood that 1) KERs will be transferred and exploited successfully, and the result applied; 2) there is an increased potential for impact from the transfer; and 3) it is possible to measure and demonstrate the impact of the transfer.

ERINN will coordinate and collaborate with other EmpowerUs WPs to support KT. All partners will contribute to the project’s Knowledge Management and Transfer activities by adhering to the protocols and assisting in the collection and analysis of KOs and the transfer of high potential KERs to end-users.

The Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology consists of the following three overall phases and is further described in detail below:

- Collect and Understand
- Validate and Analyse
- Transfer and Exploit

5.2 Knowledge Management & Transfer

This section of the PDEC outlines the stepwise process, which will be carried out within EmpowerUs Task 6.1. This methodology will see KOs identified, collected, reviewed, and prioritised to project KERs with developed KTPs. The figure below outlines an example of a full Pathway to Impact. The following subsections will refer to Figure 1. to demonstrate how each step contributes to the development of this.

Figure 1. EmpowerUs Knowledge Transfer Methodology

5.2.1 Collect & Understand

Phase 1: Capturing of KOs in an internal KO template (KOT).

Effective KT relies on careful identification and description of KOs to ensure that all key information is provided which will result in effective transfer (Figure 2). Quality control measures will be performed, to ensure that the KO(s) can be clearly understood by others who may not be experts in the relevant disciplines. Each partner will treat information from other partners as confidential unless otherwise stated and not disclose it to other parties unless the information is publicly available. It is important for all beneficiaries to note that KOs are not only the final results of research, but they can also be part of the methodology to obtain the final result, which could be an innovation for a research area or process.

Phase one aims to understand the positioning of a KO to be better able to carry out impactful KT activities. It intends to help clarify how the KO could be beneficial to different targets and end users. This step identifies potential applications, target and end users and the eventual impact of a KO. This information will also inform the development of Knowledge Output Pathways (KOPs) of KOs that progress to being a KER having been assessed as having high potential application and impact.

Figure 2. EmpowerUs Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Collect and Understand

It should be noted that KOs/KERs, especially those collected early in the project, are likely to continue to develop over the course of EmpowerUs. Collected knowledge will be periodically reviewed by ERINN and partners asked to provide updates if applicable. As the collection template will be available on the project SharePoint, partners will be able to advise ERINN if a given KO/KER needs to be updated.

PROTOCOL – Knowledge Collection

1. ERINN sends the Knowledge Output Template (KOT) to EmpowerUs WP Leaders, who will be requested to complete it and update as necessary.
2. If the WP Leader thinks another partner is better placed to provide the requested information, then they should send it on to the relevant person(s).
3. For each identified KO, all fields of the KOT should be completed. Explanations are provided under each question.
4. Completed KOTs should be sent to ERINN.
5. ERINN arranges and conducts interviews with the KO owner(s) for clarity on the knowledge collected.
6. After the interview, the KO owner(s) will receive an updated draft of the KO to check for accuracy following on from the discussion.
7. KO owner(s) are requested to respond with any corrections or suggested additions/edits in a timely manner. In particular, this review should focus on:
 - If the title of the KO(s) is sufficiently informative.
 - If the description of the KO(s) is sufficiently comprehensive for a non-expert to adequately understand the nature of the KO and to determine its possible application.
 - If the potential end-users of the KO, as well as the potential application by each of these end users is reasonable/desirable and if there are any other potential end users.

- If the KO(s) is supposed to be publicly available or is subject to IPR protection, which would influence transfer potential.
8. Once the interviewee is satisfied with the accuracy of their KOs they will be marked as “confirmed” in the KOT.
9. Once confirmed, an IP review will be carried out. This involves:
- If an IP assessment is deemed necessary, the generating partner will be asked to complete an IP Assessment Form. Assessment Forms will be reviewed by the Innovation Board chaired by ERINN, who will provide guidance as necessary until all relevant parties believe sufficient IP protection rules have been applied to the further dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the KO.

Once the IP assessment is completed, or if an IP assessment is not deemed necessary, KOs will advance to the validation and analysis stage.

5.2.2 Analyse & Validate

Phase 2: The collected KOs are reviewed and assessed for potential application and impact.

Once validated, KOs go through a Due Diligence process, whereby a more thorough examination and evaluation of the KO and its applicability and readiness for transfer will be investigated (Figure 3). Due Diligence will be undertaken so that any factors that could affect the transfer potential (confidentiality, competition, IPR) of the KO and ultimately the uptake and impact of the knowledge can be identified. Following Due Diligence, KOs will be prioritised and those with the potential to have impact will go through to the next step. An essential step in the EmpowerUs knowledge management and transfer methodology is the identification of KO applications, potential impact and respective end users (e.g., applications could be in various areas and sectors not just the one in the research area of the project) for each KO which has been assessed as having high potential application and impact.

Important aspects are prioritisation of high potential KOs and profiling target and end users to gain valuable data to inform successful Knowledge Transfer Plans. This is not a ranking of their importance but rather a method to help EmpowerUs identify where to focus transfer and exploitation efforts. For those prioritised, the expert groups will attempt to identify potential target users whose application of the knowledge would be of benefit in transferring it towards its eventual impact.

Those KOs that are validated and deemed to be of priority for the project will be re-labelled as **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** and progress to the third phase. Any KO that is not made a KER will continue to be periodically reviewed and any remaining at the end of the project will still be captured as evidence of project results for final reporting. The identification of target users in the analysis stage is critical to laying the groundwork for transfer and exploitation plans in the third phase. The exercises in this phase may also serve to identify potential stakeholders worth connecting with, even in cases where the knowledge may not yet be ready for transfer.

Figure 3. EmpowerUs Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Analyse and Validate

PROTOCOL – Analyse & Validate

At periodic intervals, ERINN will organise KO and KER “expert analysis meetings” involving the Innovation Board and the International Advisory Board.

- The frequency and makeup of these meetings will be determined in collaboration with the Project Coordinator as well as based on the current status of knowledge collection and management in the project.

The expert analysis meetings will carry out a thorough examination and evaluation of the KOs (collected so far) and their applicability and readiness for transfer. Particular attention will be paid to:

- Identification of all likely target and end-users. We encourage partners to be as specific as possible and innovative when determining potential end users.
- It is important to consider the following when profiling target and end users:
 - Understand the user’s mandate or responsibilities.
 - Consider their background knowledge, attitude, and practice in relation to the issue.
 - Understand their knowledge needs.
 - Understand what and who may influence their decisions.
 - Be aware of their preferred sources of information and knowledge.
- Identification of associated application and impact potential.

Assess the Societal Readiness Level (SRL) / Technology Readiness Level (TRL) that could inform the development of an appropriate KO Pathway, where KO requires further research, validation or scale-up.

Participants in these meetings will be asked to:

- Confirm the accuracy and feasibility of transfer both within and beyond the project (but as a direct result of the project) for each presented KO, to the best of their understanding.
- Assign to each KO a ranking to determine whether it should be prioritised as a KER based on its current status.
- Discuss and identify potential target users to whom the knowledge should be transferred to progress it towards its eventual impact.

After each expert analysis meeting, ERINN will revise the KOT to identify any progression of knowledge (such as a KO being changed to a KER).

If any questions emerge from the expert analysis meeting, ERINN will reach out to the relevant KO owners to attempt to provide an answer.

5.2.3 Transfer & Exploit

Phase 3: Carry out and report on Knowledge Transfer activities; while measuring the impact of both the activity and the application of the Knowledge by the User(s).

For each KER, a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) will be developed. Implementing an efficient KTP that is tailor-made to the needs and capacities of specific target and end users (profiled in phase 2) will maximise the chance of successful transfer resulting in uptake and application. The key to success is achieved through fully understanding the target and end user and developing the KTP around them. There are a number of steps included in the knowledge transfer plan, and there are different routes it can go down to reach its eventual impact. KTPs are the accumulation of numerous KT activities as represented in Figure 4.

KTPs will ensure KERs go through a Due Diligence process, whereby a more thorough examination and evaluation of the KER and its applicability and readiness for transfer will be investigated. Due Diligence will be undertaken so that any factors that could affect the transfer potential (confidentiality, competition, IPR) of the KER and ultimately the uptake and impact of the knowledge can be identified. The individual partner within EmpowerUs best positioned to conduct the transfer will be identified and this phase will attempt to clearly describe how the impact of EmpowerUs' KERs will be measured, even after the project has come to a close.

The work carried out in this phase will not only be important for accurately reporting the full breadth of impact of the project to the European Commission, but it will also assist all partners in carrying out exploitation activities. Not every KER transfer plan will be able to be reasonably executed during the lifetime of the project but, by delivering clear plans, the knowledge management methodology will help establish how exploitation actions within the project will feed into the overall impact of the project as a whole and help achieve the societal goals of EmpowerUs.

In collaboration with project partners, ERINN will make use of the exploitation tools and platforms developed by the EC, such as the Innovation Radar, Horizon Dashboard and Horizon Results Platform, when relevant to facilitate the exploitation of project results.

Figure 4: EmpowerUs Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Transfer & Exploit

PROTOCOL – Knowledge Transfer Planning and Exploitation

For any knowledge that has been determined to be a KER:

1. ERINN will collaborate with the Innovation Board and the owner(s) of a KER to develop a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) for each KER. In particular, this effort will focus on the following considerations regarding the first target user(s) in the plan:
 - a) Building on the impact potential identified in the validation and analysis step, ensure that a concise and compelling narrative for the opportunity/business case is developed.
 - b) The technical level of the target user; the depth of information needed; and the style of language most effective for communicating with them.
 - c) The background knowledge of the target user.
 - d) Any preconceived ideas that the target user may have relating to the area of interest.
 - e) Ways in which to relate the knowledge to examples with which the target user is familiar, or ones they can easily envisage.
 - f) The level of evidence or validation that the target user requires.
2. ERINN will be responsible for drafting these plans, which will then be provided to the project management team, project coordinator and generating partner(s).
3. Once a KTP has been drafted and reviewed, it will be opened up for feedback from the Innovation Board.
4. ERINN will work with all relevant partners to assist where possible in the translation of KTPs into exploitation activities. The nature of these exploitation activities will be highly dependent on the KER, the target user, the transferring partner, the timeline, resources available and other variable considerations. The exploitation activities themselves may be carried out within a range of externally-focused tasks.

6. Dissemination and Communication Resources

All EmpowerUs partners will dedicate time to perform communication activities and will be encouraged to engage in a two-way exchange with the public at large, and where possible the media, with the aim to show how EU research and innovation funding has a positive impact on society. Through its communication activities, EmpowerUs will demonstrate why working together in a European consortium is important in addressing a challenge that affects society.

To facilitate communication and dissemination throughout the project, a portfolio of promotional project material has been developed by ERINN.

6.1 Promotional Materials

Logo and Brand

A specific project logo has been developed to visually represent the project. The project logo is an integral part of the brand as it is, and will be, included in all project promotional materials both print and online. The EmpowerUs project logo is available in three different versions, full colour, black and white (with and without tagline) – see Brand Guide for details. Guidance on how to properly utilise the EmpowerUs logo can be found in the Brand Guide on SharePoint.

The suite of logos and Brand Guide are available in the [Task 6.2 folder](#) on SharePoint and can be requested from ERINN (contact: donnchadh@erinn.eu).

Figure 5: EmpowerUs logo with tagline

PROTOCOL – Utilising EmpowerUs Branding alongside other Institutional Branding

While it is preferable that all partners use EmpowerUs branded resources when disseminating the project's results, we recognise that some institutions will require partners to use their own institutional branding for conferences and various presentations. To balance the interests of EmpowerUs, and our contractual obligations to the EC, with various institutional requirements, we require the following requirements to be included at minimum:

- The EmpowerUs logo must be included on at least the Title Page and Conclusion/Thank You slide, however usage on all slides would be preferred.
- The EU emblem and disclaimer (GA Article 17) must be visibly present on the first and last slide.

Dissemination Templates

EmpowerUs PowerPoint presentation template and poster template have been developed for use at internal and external events when presenting the project and/or its outcomes. A word template for project deliverables and reports, and a letterhead template have also been developed.

All templates are available to download from the [Templates](#) folder on SharePoint and can be requested from ERINN (contact: donnchadh@erinn.eu).

PROTOCOL – Dissemination Templates

Partners should use the EmpowerUs templates when promoting the project's objectives or presenting project results.

Download the templates from SharePoint or contact donnchadh@erinn.eu.

- When using the PowerPoint template, choose to insert “new slide” and pick your preferred content template.
- Respect the template format (background, font and layout).
- Always ensure that the correct EU emblem, UKRI logo, acknowledgement and disclaimer are present on any EmpowerUs presentations, deliverables and reports.

Factsheet

A promotional factsheet presenting the EmpowerUs objectives and expected results has been developed. The factsheet can be shared digitally and distributed at relevant events, both virtually and in-person. The factsheet will be used to raise awareness of the project and its goals. It can be found on the EmpowerUs website or in the [Factsheet](#) folder on SharePoint or can be requested from WP6 leader, ERINN (donnchadh@erinn.eu).

PROTOCOL – Factsheet Translations

Partners are encouraged to distribute the factsheet through their networks and at relevant events. If partners wish to have the factsheet available in another language, they should follow the protocol outlined below:

- Contact ERINN (contact person: donnchadh@erinn.eu) requesting the original template with English text.
- ERINN supplies a template with the original text in English to requesting partner.
- Partner translates text (as laid out in the template) into their language.
- Partner then sends translated text back to ERINN.
- ERINN applies the translated text to the leaflet template and publishes the new version of the leaflet, after validation and sign-off from the partner responsible for the translation.

Banner

A roll-up banner to promote the EmpowerUs project has been developed. The banner contains the project logo and branding, contact details and information on the communication channels (website, Twitter, LinkedIn). The banner can be used at relevant events to raise awareness about the project. It can be found in the [Banner](#) folder on SharePoint or can be requested from WP6 leader ERINN (donnchadh@erinn.eu).

6.2 Website

The project website, (<https://empowerus-project.eu/>) has been developed following the EU’s best practice guidelines for project websites. The website is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679, GDPR) by incorporating a privacy statement and cookie bar informing website visitors about what EmpowerUs does with any personal data gathered. Google Analytics is used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website, which will be used to inform Continuous Reporting.

The project website went live and the deliverable report (D6.8) was submitted in December 2022 (M3). To ensure successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website’s content will be maintained, continuously updated and populated

with new information through the project's lifetime. The website will remain live for five years after the end of the project, serving as a valuable public resource of research information on the subject and promoting the outputs of this publicly funded research.

PROTOCOL – Requests for Updates, Posting or any other Website Activity

Any partners who wish to upload materials, news or events to the website should contact donnchadh@erinn.eu.

Partners are requested to include a link to the EmpowerUs website on their own institution/company website where possible.

6.3 Social Media

Social networking is an integral part of the EmpowerUs communication strategy. The project results and outputs will be actively disseminated through Twitter and LinkedIn (managed by ERINN). Stakeholders are encouraged to follow EmpowerUs social media, which are forums for engagement with interested parties and contribute to capacity building, showing partner expertise and knowledge through active discussions.

As with other means of communication, attention should be paid to the content being shared on social media. The consortium should determine which information to keep private and which to publish, where and to what extent. If you have questions about what is appropriate, please contact ERINN (donnchadh@erinn.eu).

In order for EmpowerUs to keep its reputation and create an engaging and thriving online community, it will be necessary to effectively manage potential risks. The following are guidelines for all partners who participate in social media and apply whether partners are posting to the EmpowerUs account, their own accounts or commenting on other accounts.

GUIDE EmpowerUs Internal Code of Social Media Conduct

Partners should try to contribute to social media channels where possible. Support can be requested from ERINN.

General Rules

- Ensure the content is yours to share (research or opinions) or acknowledge the source accordingly.
- Ensure there are no IP issues.
- Use appropriate tags and hashtags to acknowledge funding.
- Do not use offensive language, argumentative or illegal content etc.
- If you communicate publicly about EmpowerUs or EmpowerUs-related matters, you must disclose your role within the project.
- Be professional, use good judgement and be accurate and honest in your communications; unprofessional language or behaviour reflect poorly on the project, and may result in liability.
- Unless approved by the coordinator NRI, your social media name, handle and URL should not include EmpowerUs project's name or logo.

- Be mindful around controversial subjects, where emotions may run high e.g., politics. It is important to show respect for others' opinions.

Twitter and LinkedIn:

Partners wishing to communicate via the EmpowerUs Twitter and LinkedIn accounts have the following options:

- Send a short message (280 characters max) to WP6 leader ERINN (email donnchadh@erinn.eu) who can post from the EmpowerUs accounts on your behalf. Ideally, include an image or short video to make it more visually appealing.
- Refer to EmpowerUs by tagging the project (using @EmpowerUs_EU on Twitter and EmpowerUs EU Project on LinkedIn) in your own tweets/posts; ERINN will always aim to retweet/share such posts.
- Retweet/share EmpowerUs posts through your personal and institutional social media accounts.

Tips

- Social media is becoming increasingly visual — post pictures, videos, GIFs or data visualisations.
- Engage with your audience using replies, retweets/shares or tags.
- Ask questions instead of making statements to drive conversation.
- Leverage existing social media presence e.g., the host institution, researchers, team members or other relevant organisation, and tag and follow relevant accounts, particularly EC accounts (i.e., @HorizonEU, @EUScienceInnov).
- Follow the news and use trending hashtags where appropriate.

Content could include the announcement of milestones, results, scientific publications, press releases, newsletters, etc. or when the project is featured at a conference or event.

6.4 Press Releases

Press releases will be issued to appropriate media outlets (trade press, journals, web portals) to ensure that industry, communities, civil society, policymakers, and the wider community are aware of the project, its objectives and its later outcomes. The strategy is intended to ensure that there is media coverage at local, regional, European and international levels. WP6 leader ERINN will share project news through internal (consortium mailing list and partner networks) and external (press releases, social media, etc.) channels, which ensures a broad awareness of the project across the spectrum of relevant stakeholders. Partners are encouraged to publish articles and press releases at regional, national, and international levels, making use of their own communication networks and channels. ERINN can support partners in these activities.

PROTOCOL – Press Releases

Partners should notify ERINN if there is news suitable for an official project press release:

- ERINN will develop a draft and seek approval from the EmpowerUs Coordination team.

- Once approved, press releases will be disseminated using appropriate channels.
- They will be uploaded to the project website and all partners are encouraged to distribute at national or regional level.
- Where necessary the partners can adapt the press releases to customise them to their audience and if needed translate the articles.

NOTE: Partners may also initiate the writing of press releases (e.g. local, national). ERINN can then support writing and editing if required. Partners are asked to provide a short summary in English if the original communication is in another language. Partners who publish any article/press release at a regional or national level must send a copy to ERINN and where possible provide metrics to demonstrate uptake by other news channels/readership.

6.5 Other Resources and Tools

Other promotional material will be developed later in the project, such as social media visuals, GIFS and short-videos clips to promote the project. Additional promotional material can be developed as required, depending on budget availability and considering sustainability. Please contact ERINN (donnchadh@erinn.eu) with any other ideas for promotional material to support your communication and dissemination activities.

7. Dissemination and Communication Activities

The purpose of EmpowerUs' dissemination and communication activities is to make the project, its results and activities known to society at large so that all stakeholders, also beyond the project's own community, will be able to understand its messages. All EmpowerUs partners will dedicate time to perform dissemination and communication activities and will be encouraged to engage in a two-way exchange with the public at large, and where possible the media, with the aim to show how EU research and innovation funding has a positive impact on society. Through its dissemination and communication activities, EmpowerUs will demonstrate why working together in a European consortium is important in addressing a challenge that affects all societies.

A key component of the EmpowerUs dissemination and communication strategy is co-development by ongoing engagement with key stakeholders and as the project progresses, it will be critical to ensure that the project outcomes are effectively and efficiently transferred to the relevant applications by policy, community, and research users, etc. A distinct strategy will be applied to each targeted audience, using appropriate messages, means, and language. In order to effectively promote and spread awareness about the EmpowerUs concept and results so as to achieve the expected impacts, the dissemination and communication tools and activities (Table 7) will be designed and implemented by the consortium and coordinated and monitored by WP6.

Table 7. Dissemination and Communication Activities & KPIs

Tools	Academics	Business/ Industry	Policy/ Decision makers	Citizens & Society	Other
COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES					
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>The project website will constitute the main communication tool as it provides easy access to a broad audience around the world. The website has been designed following the best practice guidelines for EU project websites.</p> <p>Target: 6,000 visits over the 3-year project duration</p>					
Project branding and promotional materials	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Project branding and promotional materials will be produced for relevant events and meetings for raising awareness about the project and triggering the interest of stakeholders to visit the website and stay informed about the project’s progress. Promotional materials include the banner and project factsheet.</p> <p>Target: The promotional material will reach >5,000 people</p>					
Press releases	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Press releases will be produced regularly making use of a range of services and publications aiming at increasing awareness about the project’s objectives, progress and outcomes.</p> <p>Target: 6 press releases to be issued leading to publication of at least 12 articles</p>					
Promotional articles	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Additional promotional articles will be written and posted on the project website, throughout social media, in relevant magazines and stakeholder networks.</p> <p>Target: 30 promotional articles will be written and shared</p>					
Social Media and Campaign	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>The project will have a LinkedIn page and a Twitter account. All project partners’ social media outlets will share content and point out the relevance for their specific target groups, and thus direct their audience to EmpowerUs’ channels and website. In doing so, the consortium will reap the benefits of the partners’ combined audience base, while building a strong brand that is able to live beyond the 3-year project and thus have an extended impact on sustainable, inclusive and resilient coastal development. By adding relevant hashtags (#HorizonEurope, #SustainableDevelopment, #MarSocSci), EmpowerUs will be further amplified.</p> <p>Target: The social media accounts will reach more than 10,000 people</p>					

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES					
Policy Briefs			✓		
<p>Policy Briefs will be produced as part of WP5. These policy briefs will be widely distributed to local, national, regional and European policy actors, made available on the project website and distributed through partners' well-established networks.</p> <p>Target: At least 6 policy briefs will be published and will have >150 downloads</p>					
Events and Workshops	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>The consortium will participate in at least 15 relevant international events/conferences/workshops to raise awareness about the project. It will also host 12 workshops at the TCLs. Two Ocean Literacy events will be hosted at each TCL (a total of 12 Ocean Literacy events), in which OL resources will be shared with participants at the events.</p> <p>Target: The 12 workshops will reach >300 people, while the OL resources produced and shared at OL events will reach >1,000 people</p>					
Scientific Publications	✓				
<p>The consortium will publish at least 6 open access articles over the three-year project. A selection of science, industry and social science journals have been identified and are included in Table 9.</p> <p>Target: 6 open access articles</p>					

External Events

All partners have a responsibility to engage the public in their research activities and results and take advantage of the potential for public interest that EmpowerUs generates. Partners are encouraged to initiate dissemination activities that are appropriate for the irrespective contributions and ERINN can provide support as required. Examples include live broadcasts, institute open days, etc.

The project results will also be presented as oral presentations, posters, etc. at major international meetings and conferences of relevance to EmpowerUs. Conferences, seminars, workshops, and other meetings are very useful forums to consult with EmpowerUs target audiences in a face-to-face capacity and to address issues relevant to the work done in the project. International and sector relevant conferences, meetings, etc. will be frequently attended to communicate the results of the project to the maximum number of persons. See protocol for public outreach activities below.

Table 8 shows a list of potential events that may be of interest to EmpowerUs partners or stakeholders. These events will be added to the project website.

Table 8. Relevant events for EmpowerUs consortium and stakeholders

Event	Location	Date
World Water Day	Global	Annually in March
World Ocean Day	Global	Annually in June
World Earth Day	Global	Annually in April
World Biodiversity Day	Global	Annually in May
World Environment Day	Global	Annually in June
World Wetlands Day	Global	Annually in February
EU Green Week	Europe + Global	3-11 June 2023 (Annually in June)
European Maritime Day	Brest, France	24-25 May 2023 (Annually in May)
MARE People & the Sea Conference	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	26-30 June 2023 (Bi-annually in June/July)
Træna Winter Festival	Træna, Norway	February 2023
Blue Justice Conference	Copenhagen, Denmark (hybrid)	23-24 March 2023
2023 Stone Living Lab Conference: Nature-Based Coastal Resilience in Urban Settings	Boston, USA	20-26 April 2023
Geo-Resilience 2023	Cardiff, Wales	28-29 March 2023
Conference: Sustaining, knowing and 'living' the Blue? Coastal communities as places to belong across generations	Trondheim, Norway	15-16 June 2023
XXIXth European Society for Rural Sociology Congress: Crises and the futures of rural areas	Rennes, France	3-7 July, 2023
UN Ocean Decade Events	Global	2021-2030

PROTOCOL – Public Outreach Activities – Internal and External Events

- Partners should inform the Project coordinator and ERINN of their planned outreach activities so they can be promoted.

- Partners should inform other partners about the event via email. If the planned outreach activity involves the dissemination of EmpowerUs results, prior notice must be given to partners (see Section 2.2.4).
- All activities, including attendance at external events should be added to the Continuous Reporting Log, providing insight on type of activity, objectives, target audiences, reach (number of people) and the total cost allocated for the activity.
- All public engagement and outreach activities must be reported during (internal and external) reporting periods.
- ERINN will include events on the EmpowerUs website.
- ERINN will update the EC Portal on all Dissemination Activities.

Scientific Publications

The consortium will publish at least 6 open access articles over the three-year project. Table 9 includes a selection of potential science, industry and social science journals that are relevant to the project.

Table 9. Open Access Journals

Open Access Journals
Ambio
Coastal Studies & Societies
Ecology and Society
Environment and Planning D: Society and Space
Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space
Gender, Place & Culture
Geoforum
International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management
Journal of Environmental Management
Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning
LAND
Marine Policy
Maritime Studies (MAST)
Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change
Ocean & Coastal Management
PLOS ONE
Society and Natural Resources
Sustainability
Sustainability Science

8. PDEC Monitoring and Evaluation

The PDEC functions as an operation manual and will be updated throughout the project. WP6 leader ERINN will continue to review and amend the PDEC in line with the latest PDEC activities and project results. As part of the revision process, each subsequent version of this deliverable will be validated by the consortium. Furthermore, the project coordinator (NRI) and project partners will also review the PDEC at each review stage and provide recommendations. The current version will function as the operational manual and will be revised as part of D6.4 – Updated PDEC (M18 – March 2024) and again as part of D6.5 – Final PDEC (M36, September 2025).

9. Partners involved in the work

All partners are expected to carry out dissemination and exploitation activities as well as communication activities (Table 10). ERINN will provide coordination and support to all activities.

Table 10. WP6 Person-Months per partner

Partner	WP6 Person-Months
NRI	6
ERINN	36
AAU	3.5
UFZ	1.5
RURALIS	1.1
ATU	20
UAB	14
LMU	6
CMMI	6
LUKE	6
KPH	6
UNG	6
ANELEM	6
AF	6
QUB	1.5

Appendix 1: Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
D#.#	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KO	Knowledge Output
KT	Knowledge Transfer
KTP	Knowledge Transfer Plan
OA	Open Access
OL	Ocean Literacy
PDEC	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Activities
TCL	Transition Coastal Lab
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

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